

Spectrum of Hematological Disorders in Bone Marrow Aspiration at Tertiary Care Hospital

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Abstract:

Introduction: Hematological disorders are quite frequent in all age groups. Most of these hematological disorder present as anemia. Bone marrow aspiration is a relatively safe procedure done for the diagnosis and management of hematological disorders.

Aims and Objectives: The present study aimed to evaluate the spectrum of various hematological disorders diagnosed on bone marrow aspiration.

Material and Method: It was 2 years descriptive cross sectional study conducted in the clinical pathology section of Department of Pathology of Pt. J.N.M Medical College, Raipur.

Result: Out of 102 cases, 60 (62.7%) were males and 34 (37.3%) were females. The age range was from 8 months to 70 years. Various disorders seen were acuteleukemia (43.1%), megaloblasticanemia (15.8%), chronic myeloid leukemia (13.8%), reactive marrow (9.9%), erythroid hyperplasia (4.9%), microcytic Anemia (3.9%), idiopathic thrombocytopenic purpura (2.9%), lymphoma spill over(2.9%), acute on chronic leukemia (0.9%), multiple myeloma (0.9%) and drug induced bone marrow suppression (0.9%). Most common bone marrow diagnosis of on malignant haematological disorder were megaloblasticanemia followed by reactive marrow. In hematological malignancies most common were acute leukemias followed by chronicleukemias.

Conclusion: Bone marrow aspiration remains an important tool to arrive in the diagnosis of wide range of hematological disorders.

Keywords: Bone Marrow Aspiration, Leukemia, Megaloblastic Anemia.

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Introduction

Blood is an opaque fluid consists of plasma, a pale-yellow, coagulable fluid, in which different types of blood cells are suspended. These cells include erythrocytes, granulocytes, lymphocytes, monocytes and platelets [1]. There are numerous blood and blood related disorders which can be diagnosed by detailed clinical examination and laboratory investigations such as complete blood count, peripheral blood smear along with biochemical analysis. When peripheral blood smear is not informative, further bone marrow examination can aid for arriving at a definitive diagnosis [2].

Bone marrow is involved in variety of haematological and non-haematological disorders. Haematological disorders include chronic anaemia, pancytopenia, aplastic anaemia, thrombocytopenic purpura, hypersplenism, acute leukaemia, Myeloproliferative Neoplasm (MPN), and haematolymphoid neoplasms. Bone marrow aspiration examination is an important tool that aids in the diagnosis and management of these disorders. The aspirate smears are useful for studying the morphology of cells and for obtaining a differential cell count. [3, 4]. Bone marrow aspiration specimens are useful in further diagnostic assays including

cytochemical and special staining, immune phenotyping cytogenetic analysis and molecular studies. It may be useful in establishing the diagnosis of storage diseases and metastatic non-haemopoietic malignancies or when a leuco-erythroblastic peripheral blood picture is present. Deviations from the normal may be qualitative with abnormal cell morphology or quantitative with aplasia, hypoplasia or hyperplasia. [5,6,7]

The aim of this study was to analyse the spectrum of various non-malignant haematological and malignant haematological disorders reported on BMA wherever applicable to formulate an effective and rapid method for diagnosing a wide spectrum of diseases. This study will highlight the diagnostic utility of BMA in various haematological disorders, as combined analyses are useful in achieving more accurate and informative data in some diagnostically challenging cases.

Materials and Methods

A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted on consecutive 102 BMA samples received in the Department of Clinical Pathology, Pt. J.N.M

Medical college Raipur, Chhattisgarh, over a period of two year from September 2022 to August 2024.

Inclusion Criteria: All consecutive BMA samples were included in the study.

Exclusion Criteria: Inadequate BMA samples were excluded from the study.

Clinical Analysis: Detailed clinical history and results of previous investigations were obtained from all cases. A 2 mL Ethylenediaminetetraacetic Acid (EDTA) blood sample was collected for complete blood counts for peripheral blood film examination. BMA were performed from the same site using a one-needle technique under local anaesthesia with a lignocaine solution. The Posterior Superior Iliac Spine (PSIS) was the preferred site, while the sternum was used as the aspiration site in obese patients.

Results

The present study was done on 102 BMA smears received in the Clinical Pathology laboratory of the Department of Pathology, Pt. J.N.M. Medical College & associated Dr. B.R.A.M. Hospital, Raipur, Chhattisgarh.

Table 1: Age-wise distribution of the study population (n=102)

Age Group	Frequency	Percentage
0-10	33	32.3
11-20	24	23.5
21-30	09	8.8
31-40	15	14.7
41-50	07	6.8
51-60	08	7.8
61-70	06	5.8
Total	102	100

In the present study, 102 cases were included. Out of which the study population age ranges from 08 months to 70 years with a maximum number of cases (32.3%) belonging to 0-10 years of age group, followed by 11-20 years (23.5%), 31-40 years (14.7%), 21-30 years (8.8%), 51-6years (7.8%) and 41-50 years (6.8%), 61-70 years (5.8%).(Table No. 1)

Table 2: Sex-wise distribution of the study population (n=102)

Sex Distribution	Number	Percentage
Male	62	62.7
Female	40	37.3
Total	102	100

In the present study, out of 102 patients 62.7% of the patients were male and 37.3% of the patients were female, indicating male preponderance in present study with male to female ratio was 1.5:1. (Table No. 2)

Table 3: Indications of BMA among the study population

Indication	Frequency	Percentage
Anemia	33	32.3
Pancytopenia	23	22.5
Hepato-splenomegaly	20	19.6
Lymphadenopathy	13	12.7
Bleeding Manifestation	9	8.8
Fever	4	3.9
Total	102	100

The most common indication was anaemia under evaluation 33(32.3%) followed by pancytopenia 23(22.5%). Other indications included organomegaly (hepato-splenomegaly and lymphadenopathy), bleeding manifestation and fever. [Table 3]

Table 4: Spectrum of BMA among the study population

Spectrum	Cases	Percentage
Acute Leukemia	44	43.1
Megaloblastic Anemia	16	15.8
Chronic Leukemia	14	13.8
Reactive Marrow	10	9.9
Erythroid Hyperplasia	05	4.9
Microcytic Anemia	04	3.9
ITP	03	2.9
Lymphoma Spill Over	03	2.9
Acute On Chronic Leukemia	01	0.9
Multiple Myeloma	01	0.9
Bone Marrow Suppression (Drug Induced)	01	0.9
Total	102	100

In the present study maximum number of cases were of Acute Leukemia found in 44(43.1%) of cases followed by megaloblastic anemia in about 16 (14.7%) of cases, chronic myeloid leukemia (13.8%), reactive marrow (9.9%), erythroid hyperplasia (4.9%), microcytic anemia (3.9%), idiopathic thrombocytopenic purpura (2.9%), lymphoma spill over(2.9%), acute on chronic leukemia (0.9%), multiple myeloma(0.9%) and drug induced bone marrow suppression (0.9%) of cases respectively.[Table 4].

Among non malignant haematological disorder, 35 cases of anaemia, majority were of megaloblastic type 16(15.8%) cases and microcytic anemia 04 (3.9%) cases respectively.

Among malignant haematological disorder, 67 cases of leukaemia majority were of acute leukemia 44(43.1%) cases and outnumbered chronic leukaemia 14 (13.8%) cases respectively.

Figure 1: Bone marrow aspirate smear showing hypercellular marrow with increase erythropoiesis suggestive of erythroid hyperplasia (400X)

Figure 2: Bone marrow aspirate smear showing predominance of early and intermediate normoblast with megaloblast, suggestive of Megaloblastic anaemia(400X)

Figure 3: Bone marrow aspirate smear showing blast > 80% indicating feature of acute leukemia (1000X)

Figure 4: Bone marrow aspirate smear showing hypercellular marrow with presence of myeloid series cells with increased myelocytes, neutrophils and basophils suggestive of chronic myeloid leukemia (1000X)

Figure 5: Bone marrow aspirate smear showing increase number of plasma cells so feature are of Multiple Myeloma(1000X)

Figure 6: Bone marrow aspirate smear showing increase number of megakaryocyte so feature were suspicious of Immune thrombocytopenia .(400X)

Discussion

BMA is indicated when a patient presents with features of anemia (generalized weakness, fatigue, breathlessness), pancytopenia, organomegaly (hepatosplenomegaly, lymphadenopathy), bleeding tendency and fever.

The present study titled “Spectrum of Bone Marrow Aspiration At Tertiary Care Centre” was carried out at the Department of Pathology Pt. J.N.M. Medical College Raipur and associated Dr. B.R.A.M.

Hospital Raipur for 2 year. Total of 102 cases of BMA smears were studied.

There are many studies on bone marrow aspiration and the spectrum are varied for habits of individuals, drug history, and infections. The observation of the present study was compared and correlated with recent published literature on these relevant parameters.

Table 5: Comparison of peak age of presentation in various studies.

S.No	Authors	Year of Study	No. of cases	Age Range Years	Peak Age Incidence
1	Pudasaini S et al[11].	2012	57	9m-75y	31-45year
2	Satyasri K et al[10]	2018	120	1m-85 y	0-10 year
3	M. Atchyuta et al[9].	2019	375	13m-83y	31-40 year
4	N Sangeetha et al.[8]	2020	176	11m-70y	21-30 year
5	NiraliV et al.[7]	2020	63	11m-67y	41-50 year
6	Fatima Arshad et al.[6]	2021	756	7m-85y	21-30 year
7	Piplani G et al.[5]	2022	100	9m-85y	50-59 year
8	Ali Dogan et al.[4]	2022	500	18m-87y	35-67 year
9	Gupta C et al.[3]	2023	323	5m-85y	11-20 year
10	Sanjana et al.[2]	2024	48	4m-80y	60-80year

11	Renuka Verma et al.[1]	2024	518	3m-86y	21-30 year
12	Present study	2024	102	8m-70 y	0-10 year

In the present study, the participating patient's ages ranged from 8m to 70 years, which were in concordance with the findings of N Sangeetha et al.[8] (2020), where age ranged from 11m-70 years, Nirali V et al.[7] (2020) where cases age ranging from 11m-67 years, and Pudasaini et al.[11] (2012) with age group belonging to 9m-75 years. However, the study conducted by Gupta C et al.[3] where age ranged from 5m-85 years, Sanjana et al.[2] where age ranged from 4m-80 years and Renuka Verma et al.[1] where age ranged from 3m-86 years which was in discordance in the age group of patients with the current study.(Table No. 5)

The present study found that the maximum number of cases belonged to the 0-10 years age group (32.3%), followed by the 11-20 years age group (23.5%). This was in concordance with the findings of Satyasri K et al.[10] (2018) where the maximum number of cases belonged to the 0-10years age group at 28% respectively. However, in the study conducted by Renuka Verma et al.[1] (2024), Fatima Arshad et al.[6] (2021)and N Sangeetha et al.[8] (2020) the maximum number of cases belonged to the age group 21-30 years, Sanjana et al.[2] (2024) the maximum number of cases belonged to the age group 60-80 years, which was in discordance with the present study. (Table No.5)

Table 6: Sex-wise distribution of study population in various studies.

S.No	Authors	Year of study	Number of cases	Male: Female
1.	Pudasaini S et al.[11]	2012	57	1.1:1
2.	Satyasri K et al.[10]	2018	120	1.4:1
3.	M. Atchyuta et al.[9]	2019	375	1.1:1
4.	N Sangeetha et al.[8]	2020	176	1.1:1
5.	Nirali V et al.[7]	2020	63	1:1.25
6.	Fatima Arshad et al.[6]	2021	756	1.8:1
7.	Piplani G et al.[5]	2022	100	1.7:1
8.	Ali Dogan et al.[4]	2022	500	1.2:1
9.	Gupta C et al.[3]	2023	323	1.06:1
10.	Sanjana et al.[2]	2024	48	1.08:1
11.	Renuka Verma et al.[1]	2024	518	1.3:1
12.	Present Study	2024	102	1.5:1

In the present study, a total of 102 cases were included out of which 62 were male and 40 were female. Male preponderance was observed in the present study and the male: female ratio was 1.5:1 which was in concordance with the study conducted by Renuka Verma et al.[1] (2024), Gupta C et al [3] (2023), Piplani G et al.[5] (2022)and Satyasri K et al [10] (2018) were male: female ratio was 1.3:1, 1.6:1, 1.7:1 and 1.4:1 consecutively. Other studies

conducted by Sanjana et al [2] (2024), Ali Dogan et al.[4] (2022), N Sangeetha et al.[8] (2020) and M Atchyuta et al.[9] (2019) observed male preponderance in their studies but the male-female ratio was different from the present study. However, in studies conducted by Fatima Arshad et al.[6] (2021) female preponderance was observed, and the male: female ratio was 1:1.25 which was discordant with the present study. (Table No. 6)

Table 7: Presenting symptoms of patients in the study population in various studies.

S.No	Authors	Year of Study	1 st Most common indication	2 nd Most common indication
1	Pudasaini S et al ¹¹ .	2012	Pancytopenia	Bicytopenia
2	Satyasri K ¹⁰	2018	Anaemia	Pancytopenia
3	Nirali V et al ⁷	2020	Pancytopenia	Anemia
4	Ali Dogan et al ⁴ .	2022	Pancytopenia	Anemia
5	Sanjana et al ² .	2024	Pancytopenia	Anemia
6	Renuka Verma et al ¹	2024	Anemia	Suspected malignancy
7	Present Study	2024	Anemia	Pancytopenia

In the present study, the most common indication was anemia (75%), followed by pancytopenia which was seen in 40% patients. Almost similar features were seen in a study conducted by Satyasri et al.[10] (2018), where the most common indication was anemia (77%), followed by pancytopenia (46%).

However, the study conducted by Renuka Verma et al.[1] (2024) observed most common indication was anemia (68.6%), followed by suspected malignancy (54%) which was discordant with the present study. (Table No.7).

Table 8: Comparison of the spectrum of BMA among various studies

S.No	Authors	Year of Study	Non-malignant haematological disorder	Malignant haematological disorder
1	Pudasaini S et al.[11]	2012	Erythroid Hyperplasia	Acute Leukemia
2	Satyasri K et al.[10]	2018	Erythroid Hyperplasia	Acute lymphoblastic leukemia
3	M. Atchyuta et al.[9]	2019	Erythroid Hyperplasia	Chronic Myeloid Leukemia
4	N Sangeetha et al.[8]	2020	Megaloblastic Anemia	Acute myeloid leukemia
5	Nirali V et al.[7]	2020	Megaloblastic Anemia	Acute Leukemia
6	Fatima Arshad et al.[6]	2021	Megaloblastic Anemia	Chronic Leukemias
7	Piplani G et al.[5]	2022	Anemia	Myeloproliferative neoplasms
8	Ali Dogan et al.[4]	2022	Normal bone marrow	Acute leukemia
9	Gupta C et al.[3]	2023	Megaloblastic Anemia	Acute leukemia
10	Sanjana et al.[2]	2024	Erythroid hyperplasia with megaloblastic maturation	Acute myeloid leukemia
11	Renuka Verma et al.[1]	2024	Megaloblastic Anemia	Acute lymphoblastic leukemia
12	Present Study	2024	Megaloblastic Anemia	Acute Leukemia

In the present study, the most common non-malignant haematological disorder was megaloblastic anemia (17%) which was concordant in studies conducted by Renuka Verma et al [11] (2024), Gupta C et al.[3] (2023), Fatima Arshad et al.[6] (2021), Nirali. Vet al.[7](2020), and N Sangeetha et al.[8] (2020).

However, the studies conducted by Sanjana et al [2] (2024), Ali Dogan et al [4] (2022), M Atchyuta et al [9] (2020) and Satyasri K et al [10] (2018) observed Erythroid hyperplasia was the most non-malignant haematological disorder which was discordant with the current study.

In the present study the most common malignant haematological disorder was Acute leukemia which was concordant with studies done by Renuka Verma et al [1] (2024), Sanjana et al [2] (2024), Gupta C et al.[3] (2023), Ali Dogan et al [4] (2022), Nirali. V et al.[7] (2020), N Sangeetha et al [8] (2020).

However, Piplani G et al [5]. (2022), Fatima Arshad et al.[6] (2021), M Atchyuta et al.[9] (2019) showed the most common malignant haematological disorder was Chronic leukemia which was discordant with current study (Table No. 8)

Conclusion

The BMA is important diagnostic procedures for the diagnosis of various haematological and disorders. The spectrum of haematological conditions is very wide; therefore, bone marrow aspiration examination is a useful test to reach a final diagnosis.

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